

INNOVATION AND DEVELOPMENT

**HORIZONTAL EXCHANGE OF
INFORMATION - INSTITUTIONAL
IMPACT ON ENTREPRENEURIAL
ACTIVITY**

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Abstract: This paper investigates into the optimal innovation mechanisms and offers a legal evaluation of the optimal institutional framework under current EU anti-competitive provisions and provides a legal and economic analysis of its economic and business impacts. Analysis shows that current TFEU provisions on anti-competitive practices may deter generation and utilization of deliberately acquired productive information (entrepreneurial information) and may thus hinder optimal entrepreneurial activity.

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Introduction

The direct or indirect exchange of deliberately acquired productive information under an umbrella of the regulating competition policy is one of the contentious questions in current European competition law debate (see for example Bennett and Collins, 2010; Odudu, 2011). The effect of the EU competition law provisions and enforcement practices on entrepreneurial incentives for generation and utilisation of deliberately acquired productive information remains inconclusive and offers ample field for further research. This paper considers the current competition law provisions, their effects on businesses, and finally suggests an improved regulatory response.

In pursuing goals of economic growth and maximisation of social welfare, it is important to provide incentives for innovation and technological progress. Enterprises must invest in new products and processes and in this process they face substantial costs associated with innovation that they often cannot bear individually. To this, firms have responded with mergers and by co-operating with each other, thus sharing costs, pooling risks and complementing or enhancing individual capabilities (Lorentzen and Mollgaard, 2006). The future effects of inter-firm collaborations are difficult to evaluate, especially under the

conditions of uncertainty surrounding the process of technological change, and it is these effects that are the principle target of the EU's anti-competitive practices. Deviations from conditions that provide level playing fields for firms, like for example an exchange of information between undertakings, are perceived as infringements of EU competition law provisions (see for example Eilmansberger, 2005).

Hence, understanding the effects of the current Article 101 Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union, OJ C115/47, 9.5.2008 (hereinafter the TFEU), on undertakings, businesses and their innovative activities might be significant. Whereas it is generally accepted that entrepreneurship and innovation are relevant for economic progress (see for example Ross and Scherer, 1990; Tirole, 1988), their relationship with the current competition law provisions remains controversial. The analysed Article 101 TFEU and vague evaluation criteria for when an information exchange amounts to an infringement of Article 101 TFEU may well deter generation and utilisation of deliberately acquired productive information (*entrepreneurial information*) and may thus hinder entrepreneurial activity.

The first part of paper starts with a survey of a law and economics literature on the types of information to establish when and in which conditions an exchange of information should not be regarded as an infringement of current Article 101 TFEU. The second part (based on the provided set of economic criteria) critically comments on the current application of Article 101 TFEU and related decisions where the need for statutory reform appears recommendable. A conclusion is provided in the last section.

Entrepreneurial information - A synthesis of law and economics scholarship

It is commonly contended and well substantiated that competition is essential for maximization of social welfare and for inducement of the innovation process, which is regarded as one of the most important driving force enabling competitiveness. This section identifies several law and economics principles which might provide policy makers with additional assessment tools for establishing whether the exchange of information could have an adverse affect on competition, and tries to compress them into a general principle.

Information is a key factor in strategic decision-making and the main reason competition authorities are concerned with the exchange of information among competitors (the horizontal level) is that this practice can help firms monitor each other's behaviour. Monitoring is an essential element of collusion and allows firms to better and more promptly detect deviations facilitating the emergence of a collusive outcome (Buccirossi, 2008b). In addition, one of very important findings of economic scholarship is the notion that to tell nothing is always to say something. What that something is depends on the type of market. In some markets, parties (entrepreneurs, undertakings, competitors) who receive no information on the quality of a product will for example presume it is average in quality (Akerlof, 1970). Thus, any type of information exchanged between undertakings may raise expectations of the other party and

may induce certain behaviour of competitors to whom this information has been transmitted.

Would this then imply that the simple rule of banning all information exchanges between undertakings should be introduced and enforced? This may indeed be a straightforward argument, yet the economic literature identifies several arguments supporting a more prudent approach.

Law and economics literature identifies several principles which could be applied as an additional reference for establishing the essential features of an information exchange in the light of a possible competition law infringement (De Geest and Kovac, 2009; Posner, 2001). The first major distinction should be, as Shavell (1994) argues, made between productive and redistributive information (Hirshleifer, 1971). Information is productive and has a social value when it can be used to increase the value of the good for the party that possesses it (for example when it allows people to alter their plans accordingly, thus effecting a person's allocation decisions: e.g. if a war has in fact come to an end, it may now be worth planting hops again; while if there are valuable minerals under a plot of land, it may not be worth planting hops on it). The transaction costs of resource allocation would be reduced by more than the information costs, or directly affect the final resource allocation. The effects of productive information are, for example, improvements in production functions, interpreted in the widest sense to include the possible production of new commodities, the discovery of new resources (innovation) etc. (For example, the productive value of inventing a new fertilizer is its contribution to overall production by, for example, the ability to grow better potatoes at a cheaper cost.)

Since productive information can be used to produce more wealth, efficiency demands that strong incentives are given to generate and utilize such information. Note that the effort to acquire this productive information is socially desirable as long as the cost of generating it is lower than its expected value ($C^p < p V$). Thus, obviously a voluntary exchange of productive information between competing undertakings (the horizontal level) should be allowed, and should not be regarded as a competition law infringement.

Conversely, mere redistributive information has no social value and does not lead to any improvement in productive arrangements. It merely shifts wealth due to the price revaluations that take place upon utilisation of the information. (For example, in the case of new fertilizer for potatoes, redistributive information increases the value of shares held by the inventor.) Despite this, individuals would have the incentive to use resources in a socially wasteful way in the generation of such information since they have effects on the distribution of the surplus (Hirshleifer, 1971). Investments in discovering purely redistributive information wastes resources directly and indirectly and should be discouraged (see Shavell, 1994). Moreover, one should also deter any deliberate exchange of redistributive information between undertakings. Such an exchange should be regarded as an infringement of EU competition law (i.e. Articles 101 and 102 TFEU).

De Geest (1994) introduces also the notion of *entrepreneurial information*, i.e. information which is costly to produce, either directly or indirectly, in the sense that it takes several years to obtain the expertise. The deliberate

exchange of such information between undertakings should be allowed and should not be regarded as a competition law infringement, yet any non-intentional exchange should be seen as such an infringement and be deterred (De Geest and Kovac, 2009). Entrepreneurial information is information that is costly to produce, impossible to protect via intellectual property rights and valuable to other market players so that without a right to keep that information secret, free-rider problems would discourage the production of the information (ibid). This distinction also implies that the deliberate exchange of such productive information will occur only in cases where the exchange aims at innovative activity. Otherwise, undertakings would rarely voluntarily reveal such productive information since a free-rider problem would impair previous relationship-specific investments and the related comparative advantage. Moreover, game theoretical models also show that the dominant strategy in this respect is not to reveal productive information, even though complete information sharing would be profitable (see for example Raith, 1996). Hence, a voluntary exchange of such productive information between horizontal competitors might be an indicator of their entrepreneurial and innovative activity where the expected benefits from such an exchange/activity exceed the individual ones (see also Clarke, 1983).

Obviously, by exchanging information, undertakings may pursue goals other than the restriction of competition (collusion) (Buccirosi, 2008a, p.318). Therefore, the above listed arguments in essence call for a welfare-enhancing exchange of information (exchange of productive information) as criteria for advanced competition law enforcement. Otherwise, such a *per se* illegality rule may deter undertakings from innovative activity, entrepreneurship and consequently prevent them from improving competitiveness and market efficiency. The existence of many circumstances in which information sharing is an equilibrium formed by dominant strategies makes the inference of an explicit agreement unfounded (Laffont and Martimort, 1997).

Entrepreneurial incentive stream

To establish the importance of the effects of Article 101 TEFU for enterprises, one needs to address the relevancy of exchange of information for innovation. An innovation is a simultaneous, continuous interplay between various stages, and it often requires lateral or horizontal linkages in addition to vertical relations (Jorde and Teece, 1990, 1993). Moreover, as they argue, for innovations to be commercialized, the economic system must somehow assemble all the relevant complementary assets and create an interactive and dynamically efficient system of learning and information exchange. Nowadays the knowledge flows, not only within firms but also amongst them, are gaining in importance. One of the important changes happening in the innovation process of firms is so-called “open innovation” which implies that firms are increasingly relying on knowledge assets lying beyond their boundaries for their innovations (Box, 2009). Research by Sammarra and Biggiero (2008) shows that firms exchange not only technological knowledge but also managerial and market knowledge in innovation networks. The study investigated firms engaged in innovation collaboration in a knowledge-intensive sector with complex, heterogeneous products (aerospace cluster in

Rome area). However, in many industries firms' competitive advantage depends on the access to knowledge and specialized capabilities held by other companies which is enabled by inter-firm co-operation.

When talking about innovative activities of firms we also address the issue of entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurship literature studies the processes of the discovery, evaluation and exploitation of opportunities and their effect on the creation of new undertakings (Shane and Venkataraman, 2000). The entrepreneur's main function is combining new things or innovating, introducing a new product or new quality in a product, a new method of production, a new market, or a new organisation within an industry (Schumpeter, 1934). The notions of entrepreneurship and innovation are clearly interrelated and obviously the amount of innovation would be substantially lower without the role and function of the entrepreneur. The economic literature recognises entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship as a crucial factor in economic development (van Praag and Versloot, 2007; Wennekers and Thurik, 1999).

Not only information and knowledge flows, competitive markets are also crucial for innovation and entrepreneurship. Antitrust laws protect two freedoms important for entrepreneurs: the freedom to engage in entrepreneurship and the freedom to innovate (Golodner, 2001). EU competition law is currently aimed at encouraging market competition and discouraging activities that could in any way prevent, distort or restrict it. It aims to prevent practices that restrict access to markets, for example by decreasing the market power of large firms and lowering the barriers to the entry of small businesses, thereby fostering entrepreneurial activity.

Information exchange under Article 101 TFEU:

Suboptimal anti-competition provisions

EU competition law provisions on information exchange actually impose needless transaction costs on entrepreneurs while they, *ex ante*, assess the benefits and costs of an innovative activity. Namely, Article 101 (1) TFEU prohibits all agreements, decisions or concerted practices which could in any way prevent, distort or restrict competition and automatically voids all such prohibited agreements. Obviously, the rationale for the broad, wide meaning of Article 101 of the TFEU, encompassing agreements, decisions or concerted practices, lies in the fact that if the competition rules were to operate only when an explicit, formal agreement has been made then they would have little practical use since undertakings would try to achieve their anti-competitive goals in less formal ways. Moreover, Article 101 (1) TFEU also requires that the agreement, decision or concerted practice has the object or effect of preventing, restricting or distorting competition in the Common Market.

The interpretation of those conditions has invoked intense scholarly debate in which a consensus has not yet been reached. As commentators argue, a case law analysis shows that the European Court of Justice condemns certain types of agreements on the basis of their object or purpose without any extensive market analysis; in this sense, it effectively proscribes these agreements as *per se* illegal (Craig and De Búrca, 2008; Roth and Rose, 2008). In addition,

commentators also argue that any type of information that is directly or indirectly capable of being seen as collusive behaviour cannot be exchanged without causing EU competition authorities' concerns (ibid). A survey of relevant cases also shows that the assessment criteria for whether an exchange of information infringes the EU competition provisions (except in cases of business secrets) remains unsettled and is open to a judicial assessment of the relevant facts in a disputed case (Roth and Rose, 2008).

This evident uncertainty, along with the increased probability that an entrepreneur will be subjected to anti-trust policies and procedures, combined with the vague evaluation criteria concerning when an information exchange amounts to an infringement of Article 101 (1) TFEU rules, this might all deter the generation and utilisation of deliberately acquired productive information thereby hindering innovation and entrepreneurial activity. In other words, although competition is regarded as one of the necessary preconditions for optimal entrepreneurial activity, the current application of Article 101 (1) TFEU (whose main object is the protection of perfect market competition and hence an improvement in social welfare) may actually deter generation of deliberately acquired productive information (*entrepreneurial information*), may reduce social welfare and is hence a possible source of inefficiencies.

Conclusion

Current application of the Article 101 (1) TFEU deters generation and utilisation of deliberately acquired productive information and thus consequently hinders innovation and entrepreneurial activity. Expected benefits from certain entrepreneurial activity may well be outweighed by the inefficient risk shifting and increased transaction costs assigned upon entrepreneur under these provisions. This in effect hinders the optimal level of entrepreneurial activity and may be a source of inefficiencies (thereby diminishing social welfare).

References

- Akerlof, G., 1970. "The market for lemons: Qualitative uncertainty and the market mechanism," *Quarterly Journal of Economics*, Vol.84(3), pp. 488-500
- Bennett, M., Collins, P., 2010. "The law and economics of information sharing: The good, the bad and the ugly," *European Competition Journal*, Vol.6(2), pp. 311-37
- Box, S., 2009. "OECD work on innovation - a stocktaking of existing work," STI Working Paper 2009/2, Paris : OECD, Dir. for Science, Techn. and Industry
- Buccirossi, P., 2008a. "Facilitating practices," in: Buccirossi, P. (Ed.), *Handbook of Antitrust Economics*, Cambridge: The MIT Press, pp.305-51
- Buccirossi, P., 2008b. *Handbook of Antitrust Economics*, Cambridge: The MIT Press
- Clarke, R., 1983. "Collusion and the incentives for information sharing," *The Bell Journal of Economics*, Vol.14, pp.383-94
- Craig, P., De Búrca, G., 2008. *EU law: Text, cases, and materials*, Oxford: Oxford University Press

De Geest, G., 1994. Economische analyse van het contracten-en quasi-contractenrecht: een onderzoek naar de wetenschappelijke waarde van de rechtseconomie [(Economic Analysis of Contract Law and Quasi Contracts: An Analysis of the Scientific Value of Law and Economics)], Maklu uitgevers.

De Geest, G., Kovac, M., 2009. "The formation of contracts in the draft common frame of reference," *European Review of Private Law*, Vol.17, pp.113-32

Eilmansberger, T., 2005. "How to distinguish good from bad competition under Article 82 EC: In search of clearer and more coherent standards for anti-competitive abuses," *Common Market Law Review*, Vol.42, pp.129-77

Golodner, A., 2001. "Antitrust, innovation, entrepreneurship and small business," *Small Business Economics*, Vol.16(1), pp.31-35

Hirshleifer, J., 1971. "The private and social value of information and the reward to inventive activity," *The American Economic Review*, Vol.61(4), pp.561-74

Jorde, T., Teece, D., 1990. "Innovation and cooperation: Implications for competition and antitrust," *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, Vol.4(3), pp.75-96

Jorde, T., Teece, D., 1993. "Rule of reason analysis of horizontal arrangements: Agreements designed to advance innovation and commercialize technology," *Antitrust LJ*, Vol.61, pp. 579

Laffont, J., Martimort, D., 1997. "Collusion under asymmetric information," *Econometrica: Journal of the Econometric Society*, Vol.65(4), pp. 875-912

Lorentzen, J., Mollgaard, P., 2006. "Competition policy and innovation," in: Bianchi, P., Labory, S. (Eds.), *International handbook of industrial policy*. Cheltenham: Edward Elgar, pp.115-33

Odudu, O., 2011. "Indirect information exchange: The constituent elements of hub and spoke collusion," *European Competition Journal*, Vol.7(2), pp.205-42

Posner, R., 2001. *Antitrust law*, Chicago: University of Chicago Press

Raith, M., 1996. "A general model of information sharing in oligopoly," *Journal of economic theory*, Vol.71 (1), pp.260-88

Ross, D., Scherer, F., 1990. *Industrial market structure and economic performance*, Boston: Houghton Mifflin Company

Roth, P., Rose, V., 2008. *Bellamy & child: European community law of competition*, Oxford: Oxford University Press

Sammarra, A., Biggiero, L., 2008. "Heterogeneity and specificity of inter-firm knowledge flows in innovation networks," *Journal of Management Studies*, Vol.45(4), pp.800-29

Schumpeter, J., 1934. *The theory of economic development*, Cambridge: Harvard University Press

Shane, S., Venkataraman, S., 2000. "The promise of entrepreneurship as a field of research," *Academy of Management Review*, Vol.25(1), pp.217-26

Shavell, S., 1994. "Acquisition and disclosure of information prior to sale," *The RAND Journal of Economics*, Vol.25(1), pp.20-36

Tirole, J., 1988. *The theory of industrial organization*, Cambridge: MIT press

van Praag, C., Versloot, P., 2007. "What is the value of entrepreneurship? A review of recent research," *Small Business Economics*, Vol.29(4), pp.351-82

Wennekers, S., Thurik, R., 1999. "Linking entrepreneurship and economic growth," *Small Business Economics*, Vol.13, pp. 27-56